

Archaeological networks in pre-Roman Italy: approaching new visual methodologies

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In the context of ancient southern Italy, the study of burial goods has been coloured by long-held assumptions drawn from the Classical archaeological tradition. From trade and exchange to mobility and migration, the Greek and Italic communities of the region have been subject to an outdated agenda that not only limits our understanding of their identities, but also obscures the connections between them. In the same vein, social interaction amongst these groups has largely been viewed through a Hellenised lens, and while network research has proliferated in recent years (Blake 2014, Donnellan 2019, Donnellan 2020), south Italian archaeological data has seldom been subject to contemporary methods of digital analysis.

The following paper reframes our understanding of Italian connectivity through a novel and systematic network analysis of burial goods, spanning from the Iron Age to the Classical period. Drawing together affiliation networks (Mills 2017, 383) and spatial data, it seeks to identify ties between a diverse range of human and material agents, and is underpinned by two key questions: (1) how were personal and communal identities constructed in south Italian burial kits; and (2) what do these findings reveal about the nature of social networks and cultural interaction in the region? These questions are explored via statistical analyses conducted in R (Peeples 2011), and are complemented by a new method of network visualisation which clearly illustrates connections at various regional and interpersonal scales. While the preliminary results suggest that indigenous groups played a leading role in the historical processes that shaped pre-Roman Italy, this project ultimately aims to reconcile the social, geographic and agent-based factors that drove cultural engagement in the broader ancient world. This paper, then, has the potential to enliven the network research landscape, offering a heuristic and methodological contribution that intersects diverse disciplines, timespans, and landscapes.

References

- Blake, Emma. 2014. *Social Networks and Regional Identity in Bronze Age Italy*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Donnellan, Lieve. 2020. Objects That Bind, Objects That Separate. In *Archaeological Networks and Social Interaction*, edited by Lieve Donnellan, 116–45. London: Routledge.
- Donnellan, Lieve. 2019. "Modeling the Rise of the City: Early Urban Networks in Southern Italy." 6: 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdigh.2019.00015>.
- Mills, Barbara J. 2017. "Social Network Analysis in Archaeology." *Annual Review of Anthropology* 46: 379–97. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-20102116-20041423>.
- Peeples, Matthew. "Brainerd-Robinson Coefficient of Similarity R Script." 2011. Accessed January 23, 2024. <https://www.mattpeeples.net/BR.html>.